

Examining Mental Health, Wellbeing, Attitude towards Wars and Peace; A Comparative Analysis Of Militants And Non-Militants

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the relationship between mental health, well-being, and attitudes towards war and peace among militants and non-militants. The research is cross-sectional and correlational, involving 600 participants from North Waziristan, Swat, and Peshawar districts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, as well as militants. Participants were assessed using the Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS), the PERMA Profiler for well-being, and an attitude scale towards war and peace. Key hypotheses posit that poor mental health is positively correlated with war-oriented attitudes and negatively correlated with peace-oriented attitudes. Additionally, militants are hypothesized to exhibit higher levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, and lower levels of well-being compared to non-militants. Findings reveal significant positive correlations among depression, anxiety, and stress, and significant negative correlations between mental health measures and well-being. Attitudes towards peace are negatively correlated with mental health indicators, whereas attitudes towards war show minimal correlation. Comparisons between militants and non-militants demonstrate significant differences in anxiety, stress, and overall well-being, with militants displaying poorer mental health and lower well-being. ANOVA results indicate significant differences across groups in mental health measures, well-being domains, and attitudes towards peace and war. Militants score highest in depression, anxiety, and stress, and lowest in well-being and attitudes towards peace.

Keywords: Mental Health, Well-being, Attitudes towards War & Peace, Militants, Non-militants, Depression, Anxiety, Stress, PERMA Profile

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1. Introduction

Mental health and wellbeing are well-known indicators and determinants of individuals' perspectives and attitude towards war and peace. To understand these dynamics, it is particularly important to consider the regions affected by prolonged conflicts.

Also, to gauge differences among militants and non-militants, this study aimed to compare mental health, wellbeing, and attitudes toward wars and peace of the militants and non-militants. Knowledge of how these groups perceive can be helpful in offering insights to militant effects. Hence, the findings of this study would contribute to the peacebuilding and mental health by identifying key factors that differentiate militants from non-militants.

Several studies have been carried out in the world to analyze the psychological implications due to conflicts. Conflicts involving individuals and those not involved have been studied to show differences in mental health, violence, and peace perceptions. For example, the impact of mental health on ex-militants in Nigeria's region of Niger Delta tended to acknowledge the differences in well-being between militants and non-militants were measured (Brown, 2020). Similarly, the well-being of sufferers in Turkey initially was researched to identify the necessity of doing intervention programs (Sancar, 2019). In other further research, Nigerian insurgents were compared with non-insurgents to find out how their psyches fared when each was exposed to peace-building measures (Okoi, 2019). The comparative result yielded that non-militant activists had more psychological resilience than militant activists (Gardner & Atkinson, 2019). Finally, the study selected a few research and case studies from different countries to analyze the psychological effect of state oppression concerning militants and non-militants (Shay, 2021).

Similarly, in Asia, the impact of conflict on people's mental health is very high, and the variations between militants and non-militants can be distinguished. For instance, the long term effects of the conflicts in the regions like Kashmir in India have been studied with regard to the impact on the mental health of the people. Similar mental health trends are found in the Philippines; the study concluded that militants had been undergoing more trauma and stress as compared with non-militants (Schiavo-Campo & Judd, 2005). A significant difference exists in the psychological condition among the group that is militant or non-militant. In the latest one, in Sri Lanka, authors discussed post-conflict reconciliation and compared the mental health of ex-militants and non-militants and found the latter to be experiencing a better psychological adaptation (Somasundaram, 2006).

The mental health and well-being of a person are very central aspects of how stable and peaceful a society can be. Prolonged exposure to conflict and violence in Pakistan affects the attitudes towards wars and peace among militants as well as non-militants. Extensive research has underlined the psychological burden of continuous conflict, with a salient prevalence of PTSD, depression, and anxiety among populations residing in conflict-affected regions of the country. They are usually more aggressive and have more traumatic-related symptoms than non-militants, whose experiences, although distressing, are of different natures and intensities (Hartley & Cherney, 2016). Second, the sociopolitical situation within Pakistan, marked by frequent instability and occasional violence, has heightened these mental health problems and, as will be detailed further in this analysis, has come to influence popular opinions and attitudes toward peace initiatives in Pakistan (Bergen & Rothenberg, 2015). The recent research by NACTA concerning violent extremism in Pakistan also digs very systematically into the psychological and social consequences faced by militants as well as non-militants (Iqbal & Salman, 2023). Furthermore, the United Nations report on armed conflict effects indicates that the level of mental health deterioration is very high, especially in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (UNFPA, 2024). This comparative analysis seeks to delve deeper into these aspects since it gives insight into the mental health disparities in militants and non-militants and how these differences bring out respective attitudes towards conflict and peace.

Rationale

Much research has been done around the world to evaluate the effects of conflict on mental health by looking at several factors, including posttraumatic stress disorder, anxiety, and depression, among others, on the affected people. Several studies have been carried out on the effects of insurgencies, terrorism, and protracted conflicts in general on military personnel and populations. For example, Brown (2020) labeled the mental health conditions of the former militants in Nigeria's Niger Delta region and maintained that they have very high rates of trauma-related disorders. Likewise, in a paper on the effects of terror on health, general health, and resilience of terrorized populations in Istanbul, Sancar (2019) argued for the need for societal level mental health interventions. In Nigeria, Okoi (2019) compared the psychological of the former and non-insurgents in their attitudes toward the processes of peace building (Okoi, 2019). However, despite the fact that these studies are informative and give an understanding of the psychological effects of conflict, there is a significant gap in the research literature. More so, there is a dearth of cross-sectional comparison of militants and non-militants in the same conflict zone.

Specifically, in the case of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan which has been affected by long-term conflict, knowledge about the psychological state and well-being of both militants and non-militants is essential. However, a lot has been researched about the impact of conflicts on the mental health of people in general, with very little coming up to compare the psychological effects and perceptions of the two states of wars and peace between these two different categories of people. Therefore, the present study is designed to bridge this gap and make a comparative analysis of the mental health and well-being of militants and non-militants from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, thereby contributing to a better understanding of psychological processes in conflict-affected areas.

Objectives

- To examine the relationship of mental health, wellbeing and attitude towards war and peace among militant and non-militants.
- To examine difference among militant and non-militants on mental health, wellbeing and attitude towards war and peace.

Hypotheses

- H1: Depression, anxiety, and stress will be positive, and mental well-being will be negatively correlated to war-oriented attitude.
- H2: Depression, Anxiety, and Stress will be negative, and mental well-being will be positively correlated to a peace-oriented attitude.
- H3: Militants will score high on depression, anxiety, and stress and attitude towards war as compared to non-militants.
- H4: Militants will score low on mental well-being (Positive emotions, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishment) and attitude towards peace as compared to non-militants

Conceptual Model

2. Methodology

Research design

The present study was cross-sectional and correlational in nature.

Population and Sample

The study population comprised militants and non-militants from North Waziristan, Swat, and Peshawar districts in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. A total of 600 participants were involved, divided into four groups: 150 from each operational area (Swat, North Waziristan, Peshawar), and 150 militants. The data collection adhered strictly to legal procedures, ensuring accuracy and validity. All militants included in the study were legally declared as such following due legal process. The information gathered was factual and professional, focused on objective measurements without influence from personal opinions or biases.

Inclusion

Individuals above 18 years of age were included.

Instruments

Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS)

It was developed by Lovibond and Lovibond (1995) with 21- items, responses ranged from 0= no experience to 3= often or most of the time. The Alpha Cronbach was reported to be .92, .90 and .86 showing high reliability (Vingola & Tucci, 2014).

Wellbeing (PERMA Profiler)

The scale used for measuring wellbeing in the present study was PERMA profiler. It was developed by Butler & Kern (2016) with 11-points Likert scale containing 15-items. This scale is further divide into 5 domains; positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning and accomplishment. The alpha Cronbach ranged from .75 to .84 for Urdu translated version (Faran & Malik, 2021).

Attitude towards war and Peace

It was developed by Bizumic et al. (2013) having 16-items and 9-points Likert type. 8-items measure attitude towards peace and the other 8-items measure attitude towards war. The alpha Cronbach was .83 for peace subscale and .90 for war attitude subscale.

Procedure

This study focused on exploring the impact of psychosocial factors on attitudes towards war and peace in North Waziristan. The total sample size was 600 participants divided into four groups: 150 from Swat, 150 from North Waziristan (NWD), 150 from Peshawar, and 150 militants in custody. Participants were recruited with assistance from local government organizations, ensuring constructive and protected relationships were established. Ethical considerations were rigorously followed, including obtaining informed consent from participants after briefing them on the study's objectives and maintaining strict confidentiality of their personal data. Formal permissions were obtained to collect data from militants. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS 25 and AMOS 23.

3. Results

This study focused on the psychosocial determinants of attitudes towards war and peace and revealed a relationship among mental health, wellbeing and attitude towards war and peace among militants and non-militants. The results presented here are as follows:

Table 1 Relationship among mental health, wellbeing and attitude towards war and peace among militant and non-militants (n=600)

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
Depression	7.30	4.83	-					
anxiety	5.93	4.40	.711**	-				
stress	8.79	4.88	.812**	.731**	-			
Wellbeing	92.83	26.77	-.644**	-.404**	-.587**	-		
Attitude; Peace	44.77	7.73	-.282**	-.164**	-.334**	.332**	-	
Attitude; War	40.08	9.44	-.006	.023	.114**	-.069	-.195**	-

Note. M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 1 shows a positive correlation between depression and anxiety, $r = 0.711$, $p < 0.01$, depression and stress, $r = 0.812$, $p < 0.01$, and anxiety and stress, $r = 0.731$, $p < 0.01$ which shows that those who experience one mental health issue would tend to experience the other in higher severity within both groups. Significantly negative correlation coefficients were found between the measures of mental health (depression, anxiety, stress) and wellbeing; and insignificantly stronger negative correlation was noted between depression and wellbeing (-0.644 , $p < 0.01$) which means the militants and non-militants with poor mental health reported lower level of wellbeing.

Regarding attitudes towards war and peace, there are negative correlations between attitudes towards peace and mental health indicators (depression, anxiety, stress), implying that more positive attitudes towards peace are associated with better mental health outcomes (ranging from $r = -0.282$ to $r = -0.334$, all $p < 0.01$). Conversely, attitudes towards war show minimal correlations with mental health measures (ranging from $r = -0.006$ to $r = 0.114$, all non-significant or weakly significant), indicating a less pronounced relationship compared to attitudes towards peace.

Table 2 Mean scores, Standard Deviation, and t-values of militants and non-militants on depression, stress, and anxiety, wellbeing, attitude towards war and peace (n=600)

Variables	Militants (n=150)		Non-Militants (n=450)		t	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
Depression	12.91	4.26	5.22	3.33	-22.35	.141	-8.37	-7.02	2.051
Anxiety	9.81	6.06	4.54	2.63	-14.27	.000	-5.99	-4.54	1.128
Stress	14.10	3.28	6.56	3.75	-21.77	.003	-8.22	-6.86	2.140
Wellbeing	75.38	30.12	98.64	22.79	9.94	.000	18.67	18.67	0.870
Positive emotion	18.63	6.06	75.38	30.12	6.11	.000	27.86	27.86	2.612
Engagement	15.12	6.20	18.63	6.06	8.85	.000	2.38	2.38	0.573
Relationship	19.05	5.03	15.12	6.20	13.05	.000	4.64	4.64	0.708
Meaning	14.48	6.65	19.05	5.03	9.12	.000	3.56	3.56	0.775
Accomplishment	20.85	5.27	14.48	6.65	4.58	.000	5.59	5.59	1.061
Attitude; Peace	46.57	7.10	39.35	7.00	10.81	.806	5.91	8.53	1.024
Attitude; War	40.39	10.22	39.13	6.52	1.42	.000	-0.48	3.01	0.147

Table 2 compares mean scores, standard deviations, and t-values for depression, anxiety, stress, wellbeing, its subscales (positive emotion, engagement, relationship, meaning, accomplishment), and attitudes towards peace and war between militants and non-militants. Significant differences were found for anxiety, stress, wellbeing, and its subscales, with non-militants scoring significantly higher on overall wellbeing and all its subscales (positive emotion, engagement, relationship, meaning, accomplishment). Additionally, militants had significantly higher levels of anxiety and stress. Attitudes towards war were significantly higher among militants, while attitudes towards peace did not show a significant difference between the two groups. Notably, depression also did not show a significant difference between militants and non-militants.

Table 3 Mean, Standard Deviation and One-way Analysis of Variance across area on depression, stress, and anxiety, wellbeing, attitude towards war and peace (n=600)

Variables	Categories	North Waziristan		Swat		Militants		Peshawar		F (3, 596)	η^2
		M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
Mental state	Depression	8.09	3.06	4.29	2.47	12.91	4.26	3.89	2.63	260.08***	1.30914
	Anxiety	6.29	2.79	3.71	2.07	9.81	6.06	3.91	2.17	90.37***	0.45487
	Stress	10.65	2.88	5.51	2.94	14.10	3.28	4.89	3.15	306.59***	1.54325
Wellbeing	Positive emotions	16.30	5.23	19.30	5.72	15.12	6.20	20.29	6.48	25.47***	0.12818
	Engagement	15.50	4.92	20.36	3.64	14.48	6.65	21.29	4.39	69.38***	0.34923
	Relationships	16.69	5.14	22.51	4.00	13.87	6.74	23.35	3.86	122.39***	0.61605
	Meaning	16.56	6.10	20.53	5.66	14.50	7.36	23.23	4.95	62.26***	0.31338
	Accomplishment	15.76	5.38	21.71	4.13	17.41	7.37	22.55	4.13	55.33***	0.27853
Attitude towards peace		44.53	6.26	46.57	6.79	39.35	7.00	48.61	7.65	49.14***	0.24734
Attitude towards war		44.99	5.89	34.64	10.33	39.13	6.52	41.55	10.84	37.64***	0.18948

Note. M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation

Table 3 provides a comparison of mean scores, standard deviations, and one-way ANOVA results for depression, anxiety, stress, wellbeing, and attitudes towards peace and war across four different areas: North Waziristan, Swat, militants, and Peshawar.

Significant differences are observed in mental health measures across the groups. Militants have the highest mean scores for depression (M = 12.91, SD = 4.26), anxiety (M =

9.81, SD = 6.06), and stress (M = 14.10, SD = 3.28). In contrast, participants from Peshawar have the lowest scores for depression (M = 3.89, SD = 2.63), anxiety (M = 3.91, SD = 2.17), and stress (M = 4.89, SD = 3.15). The ANOVA results indicate these differences are statistically significant for depression ($F(3, 596) = 260.08, p < .001, \eta^2 = 1.30914$), anxiety ($F(3, 596) = 90.37, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.45487$), and stress ($F(3, 596) = 306.59, p < .001, \eta^2 = 1.54325$).

Wellbeing and its subscales also show significant differences across groups. Participants from Peshawar have the highest scores for positive emotions (M = 20.29, SD = 6.48), engagement (M = 21.29, SD = 4.39), relationships (M = 23.35, SD = 3.86), meaning (M = 23.23, SD = 4.95), and accomplishment (M = 22.55, SD = 4.13). Militants, on the other hand, have the lowest scores in these areas. The ANOVA results confirm significant differences for positive emotions ($F(3, 596) = 25.47, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.12818$), engagement ($F(3, 596) = 69.38, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.34923$), relationships ($F(3, 596) = 122.39, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.61605$), meaning ($F(3, 596) = 62.26, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.31338$), and accomplishment ($F(3, 596) = 55.33, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.27853$).

There are also significant differences in attitudes towards peace and war across the groups. Participants from Peshawar have the highest attitude towards peace scores (M = 48.61, SD = 7.65), while militants have the lowest (M = 39.35, SD = 7.00). For attitudes towards war, participants from North Waziristan have the highest scores (M = 44.99, SD = 5.89), while participants from Swat have the lowest (M = 34.64, SD = 10.33). The ANOVA results show significant differences for attitudes towards peace ($F(3, 596) = 49.14, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.24734$) and attitudes towards war ($F(3, 596) = 37.64, p < .001, \eta^2 = 0.18948$).

4. Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive comparative analysis of mental health, wellbeing, and attitudes towards war and peace between militants and non-militants in the regions of North Waziristan, Swat, and Peshawar. The findings reveal significant disparities across various psychosocial dimensions, highlighting the profound impact of context and experiences on individuals' mental states and perceptions.

We hypothesized that depression, anxiety, and stress would be positively correlated, and mental well-being would be negatively correlated with a war-oriented attitude. The results indicated significantly negative correlation coefficients between mental health measures (depression, anxiety, stress) and well-being, with an insignificantly stronger negative correlation observed between depression and well-being ($r = -0.644, p < 0.01$). However, attitudes towards war showed minimal correlations with mental health measures (ranging from $r = -0.006$ to $r = 0.114$, all non-significant or weakly significant). Our findings align with existing literature which demonstrates that poor mental health is inversely related to well-being. For example, Furedi et al. (2020) and Penner et al. (2020) describe how increased rates of depression, anxiety, and stress are unhealthy for the individuals. This weak correlation between war-orientation and the indices of mental health is similarly in conformity with the findings of Jamil (2018) and Sabti (2017), who noted that while war experiences can negatively impact mental health, war attitudes are not a very good predictor of an individual's mental health status. This might be due to the stress management and the other factors that relate to the complex nature of war as postulated by Hayes and colleagues (2010) and Andrew (2017). Such interactions therefore imply that other factors which are not confined to attitude towards war determine mental health and well-being. The observed relationships may be as a result of cognitive bias, whereby mental health problems lead to a change of attitude to become negative and more aggressive or the theory of positive affect whereby positive feelings and disposition enhance positive

mental health. Thus, there is a need to boost the support of the peace-related perceptions in order to improve mental health and well-being.

We hypothesized that militants would score higher on depression, anxiety, stress, and attitudes towards war compared to non-militants. Results from Table 2 show that militants have significantly higher levels of anxiety, stress, and war-oriented attitudes. Non-militants scored significantly higher on overall well-being and all its subscales (positive emotion, engagement, relationship, meaning, accomplishment). Depression and attitudes towards peace did not significantly differ between the groups. The findings confirm that militants experience higher anxiety and stress, consistent with studies indicating that high-stress environments elevate these mental health issues (Sabti, 2017; Andrew, 2017). The higher well-being scores among non-militants align with research suggesting positive social interactions and meaningful activities enhance well-being (Penner et al., 2020; Hayes et al., 2010). The non-significant differences in depression and attitudes towards peace suggest these factors are influenced by personal characteristics or conditions beyond militant activities (Jamil, 2018; Furedi et al., 2020). Higher war-oriented attitudes among militants reflect their environment's impact, while similar attitudes towards peace in both groups suggest an underlying value for peace.

We hypothesized that militants would score lower on mental well-being (positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishment) and attitudes towards peace compared to non-militants. Results from Table 2 show significant differences in anxiety, stress, well-being, and its subscales, with non-militants scoring significantly higher on overall well-being and all its subscales. Attitudes towards war were significantly higher among militants, while attitudes towards peace and depression did not significantly differ between the groups. The results support the hypothesis that militants have lower mental well-being and higher levels of anxiety and stress compared to non-militants. This is consistent with research indicating that individuals in high-stress, conflict-related environments often experience reduced well-being and increased mental health issues. Studies revealed higher level of anxiety and stress in militants exposed to stressful and traumatic environments (Sabti, 2017, Andrew, 2017).

The differences in the well-being subscales of positive emotions, engagement, relationships, meaning, and accomplishment imply the significance of these aspects for mental health; the positive social relationships and meaningful activities increase well-being (Penner et al. , 2020). The results of the higher war-oriented attitudes among militants show that their environments and experiences foster such perceptions as it has been highlighted in the literature on CAPs (Jamil, 2018). Since there were no differences identified in the perception of the two groups with regard to the peace, it can be argued that in spite of the fact that the male students have war attitudes, they might have similar attitudes to the female students with regard to the peace, which could be attributed to basic human values or beliefs. The similar levels of depression imply that this health condition might be influenced by other factors other than the militant activities only (Furedi et al. , 2020).

5. Conclusion

This systematic review focuses on the strong relationship between mental health, SWB and perception of war and peace among militants and non-militants. Some of the findings show that militants have higher depression, anxiety, and stress scores and lower well-being scores and higher war prone cognition scores. On the other hand, non-militants are found to be psychologically healthier, having higher subjective well-being and are less likely to support the use of force. These findings confirm the hypothesis that psychosocial factors are related to conflict attitudes and indicate that respondents with a poor mental

health status are likely to hold negative attitudes toward peace and are inclined toward war-like ideas. This insight focuses on improving the psychological well-being of individuals to promote positive perceptions of peace especially in the affected areas. The study recommends that more focus should be placed on the mental health of the people in conflict areas and militants noting that enhanced mental health will enhance conflict transformation and peace building processes. In future studies, it is recommended to examine the nature of these associations and identify ways of enhancing mental health and enhancing constructive perceptions of conflict in affected communities.

6. Limitations and Recommendations

This study, while comprehensive, has several limitations. First, the cross-sectional design restricts the ability to infer causality between mental health, well-being, and attitudes towards war and peace. Future research should consider employing longitudinal designs to better understand the causal relationships between mental health, well-being, and attitudes towards conflict. Second, the sample was drawn from specific regions (North Waziristan, Swat, Peshawar) and militants, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or populations. Generalizations could be strengthened even more by increasing sample diversity to include militants from several other regions and different backgrounds. Thirdly, self-report measures on mental health and attitude are deeply flawed by the bias of social desirability and, therefore, a significant limitation to the authenticity of the data. Mixed methods, including qualitative approaches, can provide greater psychosocial depth about attitudes regarding war and peace. Finally, although the study controlled for several other confounding factors, other unmeasured variables may have impacted the results—variables such as socioeconomic status or prior trauma. Furthermore, the self-report limitations will be reduced with the addition of objective measures of mental health status, i.e., clinical assessments. Interventions to foster mental health and well-being will be specially designed and tested in areas where recent conflicts occurred to estimate how much they help foster peace-oriented attitudes. Collaboration with local communities and stakeholders is crucial to achieve culturally sensitive and sustainable implementation of such interventions.

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